

SYNTHESIS OF 6H(CHLORINE)-BENZOTHIAZOLIN-2-ONE(-THIONE) DERIVATIVES

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Abstract. In this work, benzothiazoline-2-thione obtained from the reaction of *o*-aminothiophenol with thiourea was subjected to acylation with *p*-methoxybenzoyl chloride in the presence of benzene at 80 °C for 2h. As a result, (4-methoxyphenyl)-2-thioxobenzo[d]thiazol-3(2H)-yl) methanone was successfully synthesized, and its reaction with hydrazine hydrate was subsequently investigated. Furthermore, a novel and previously unreported catalyst-free microwave-assisted method was developed for the high-yield synthesis of 2-substituted 6H(Cl)-1,3-benzothiazoles within a short reaction time. In this approach, *o*-aminothiophenol (or 6-chloro-*o*-aminothiophenol) was reacted with various aldehydes in a microwave reactor at 65 W, and the influence of reaction time on the synthesis process was systematically examined. It was observed that increasing the microwave irradiation time led to a significant improvement in product yields. Under optimized conditions, the reaction of *o*-aminothiophenol and aldehydes in a 1:1 molar ratio using an ethanol–water (1:1) solvent system afforded 2-substituted 6H-1,3-benzothiazoles in moderate to good yields within 3-4 minutes and in high yields after 5 minutes of irradiation. Similarly, the reaction of 6-chloro-*o*-aminothiophenol with aldehydes under the same molar ratio and solvent system in a microwave reactor resulted in moderate to good yields within 4-6 minutes and high yields within 7 minutes, leading to the efficient synthesis of 2-substituted 6(Cl)-1,3-benzothiazole derivatives.

Keywords: *o*-aminothiophenol, *p*-methoxybenzoyl chloride, 3-methoxybenzaldehyde, (4-methoxyphenyl)2-thioxobenzo[d]thiazol-3(2H)yl)methanone, -(4-chlorophenyl)-6(chlor)-benzothiazole.

Introduction

According to the literature, numerous benzothiazole derivatives have been developed that exhibit a wide range of biological activities, including anticancer [1; 5424-5427 pp., 2; 7095-7103 pp.], antimicrobial [3; 1795-1801 pp., 4; 3681-3685 pp., 5; 5599-5608 pp.], anti-inflammatory [6; 34-38 pp.], antitubercular [7; 137-145 pp., 8; 275-281 pp.], anti-HIV (acquired immunodeficiency syndrome) [9; 868-882 pp.], antimalarial [10; 995-998 pp.], anticonvulsant [11; 1345-1349 pp.], anthelmintic [12; 459-464 pp., 13; 439-442 pp.], antioxidant [14; 2228-2232 pp.], and bactericidal [15; 118-125 pp.] properties. In addition to their

pharmaceutical applications, several benzothiazole-based compounds have been identified as fungicides [16–18], herbicides [19–21], and plant growth regulators [22–25].

In view of these findings, continued research aimed at the discovery of new biologically active substances has been undertaken, focusing on the investigation of inhibitory and growth-regulating activities of this class of compounds. Such studies are of considerable interest not only from a theoretical perspective but also from a practical standpoint, due to the broad applicability of benzothiazole derivatives in medicinal chemistry, agriculture, and related fields. Benzothiazoles possessing high synthetic potential continue to be of considerable interest to chemists and biologists. These compounds are widely recognized as important heterocyclic scaffolds in modern organic synthesis and pharmaceutical chemistry.

Below are the structural formulas of several clinically important drugs containing the benzothiazole ring system, including riluzole, ethoxzolamide, dimazole, Pittsburgh compound B, and flutemetamol, which further demonstrate the significant pharmacological relevance of this heterocyclic framework:

Materials and Methods

Benzothiazoline-2-thione, synthesized via the reaction of *o*-aminothiophenol with thiourea, was reacted with *p*-methoxybenzoyl chloride in benzene in the presence of triethylamine as a catalyst. The reaction mixture was heated at 80 °C for 2 h. Upon completion of the reaction, the resulting precipitate was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol, affording (*4*-methoxyphenyl)-2-thioxobenzothiazol-3(2*H*)-yl)methanone (**3**) with an isolated yield of 80% (Appendices I and II).

Results

The structures of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and X-ray crystallographic analysis.

¹H and ¹³C NMR Spectral data of compound 3

The synthesized (4-methoxyphenyl)-2-thioxobenzothiazol-3(2H)-yl)methanone (**3**) was reacted with hydrazine hydrate in anhydrous ethanol at 10 °C. As a result of this reaction, the expected (4-hydrazinylphenyl)-2-thioxobenzothiazol-3(2H)-yl)methanone was not formed; instead, the formation of benzothiazoline-2-thione (**2**) and 4-methoxybenzohydrazide (**4**) was observed. The resulting compounds were separated by column chromatography using a petroleum ether–ethyl acetate (10:1) solvent system.

Figure I. X-ray crystal structure of compound 4

Discussion

It is well known that the reactions of *o*-aminothiophenol with certain aldehydes have previously been investigated in our earlier studies (**26**). Continuing these investigations, a novel method not previously reported in the literature was developed for the synthesis of 2-substituted 6(H)Cl-1,3-benzothiazoles via a catalyst-free microwave-assisted protocol, enabling high yields within a short reaction time. It should be emphasized that the reactions were carried out using two different approaches (Methods **A** and **B**). According to Method **A**, a 1:1 molar mixture of *o*-aminothiophenol (**1a**) and the corresponding aldehyde was stirred in an ethanol–water (1:1) solvent system at room temperature for 4 h, while the reaction of 6-chloro-*o*-aminothiophenol (**1b**) with aldehydes was conducted under heating for 6 h. Under these conditions, 2-substituted 6(H)Cl-1,3-benzothiazoles were obtained in high yields. In Method **B**, a 1:1 molar mixture of *o*-aminothiophenol (**1a**) and aldehyde in an ethanol–water (1:1) solvent system was subjected to microwave irradiation in a chemical microwave reactor at 85 °C and 65 W. Under these conditions,

moderate to good yields were achieved within 3–4 minutes, while high yields were obtained after 5 minutes, affording product (4).

Figure II. Pharmacological activities of (4-hydrazinylphenyl)-2-thioxobenzothiazol-3(2H)-yl)-methanone predicted using the PASS (online) program.

Further microwave-assisted reactions were carried out using 6-chloro-*o*-aminothiophenol (1b) and aldehydes under identical conditions. In this case, moderate to good yields were achieved within 4–6 minutes, and high yields were obtained after 7 minutes, leading to the synthesis of products (5–7), as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1

No	Molecular formula	R _f	Melting point (°C)	Reaction yield (%) after 4 and 6 hours	Reaction yield (%) MW, 5 and 7 min
4	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ SN	0.77	112-114	83,6	94
5	C ₁₃ H ₈ SNCl	0.75	104-106	80,6	85,5
6	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ SNCIO	0.54	74-76	79,7	83
7	C ₁₃ H ₇ SNCl ₂	0.65	144-146	81	86,7

Conclusion

In conclusion, it was observed that the increase in reaction time leads to a corresponding increase in the yields of the synthesized compounds. Reactions carried out in a microwave reactor demonstrated high efficiency, providing excellent yields within short reaction times and without

the use of additional reagents or catalysts. Compared to conventional thermal methods, the microwave-assisted approach proved to be more effective and time-efficient.

Experimental Section

(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2-thioxobenzo[d]thiazol-3(2H)-yl)methanone (3)

A solution of benzothiazolin-2-thione (2.9 g, 17.4 mmol) in benzene (30 mL) was treated with *p*-methoxybenzoyl chloride (3.55 g, 20.8 mmol), followed by the addition of triethylamine (1.753 g). The reaction mixture was heated at 80 °C for 2 h. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, and the resulting precipitate was filtered. The crude product was recrystallized from ethanol to afford compound **3** as a white solid. Yield: 4.1 g (80%); Melting point: 164–166 °C; R_f = 0.50 (hexane : ethyl acetate 5 : 1). (Appendix I, II)

2-Phenyl-1,3-benzothiazole (4)

A solution of *o*-aminothiophenol (0.3125 g, 2.5 mmol) in an ethanol–water mixture (1:1, 25 mL) was treated with benzaldehyde (0.265 g, 2.5 mmol), and the resulting reaction mixture was irradiated in a microwave reactor for 5 min. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature, and the precipitate formed was filtered, washed with petroleum ether, and dried. The crude product was recrystallized from ethanol to afford compound **4** as an orange solid in 0.496 g yield (94%) with a melting point of 112–114 °C and R_f = 0.77 (A). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.12 (d, J = 7.38 Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.02 (t, J = 7.42 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.65 (t, J = 7.42 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.33–7.39 (m, 3H, ArH), 7.19–7.25 (m, 3H, ArH); m/z = 212 ([M + H]⁺).

6-Chloro-2-phenyl-1,3-benzothiazole (5)

A solution of 6-chloro-*o*-aminothiophenol (0.40 g, 2.5 mmol) in an ethanol–water mixture (1:1, 25 mL) was treated with benzaldehyde (0.265 g, 2.5 mmol), and the resulting reaction mixture was irradiated in a microwave reactor for 7 min. Upon completion of the reaction, the mixture was cooled to room temperature, and the formed precipitate was filtered, washed with petroleum ether, and dried. The crude product was recrystallized from ethanol to afford compound **5** as a light orange solid in 0.525 g yield (85.5%) with a melting point of 104–106 °C and R_f = 0.75 (A).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.19 (d, J = 8.3 Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.13 (d, J = 2.12 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.56 (dd, J = 7.61, 2.17 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.36 (t, J = 7.61 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.16 (m, 1H, ArH); m/z = 246 ([M + H]⁺). Molecular formula: C₁₃H₈ClNS.

6-Chloro-2-(3-methoxyphenyl)-1,3-benzothiazole (6)

The reaction was carried out following the same procedure as described above. A solution of 6-chloro-*o*-aminothiophenol (0.40 g, 2.5 mmol) in an ethanol : water mixture (1:1, 25 mL) was treated with 3-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.34 g, 2.5 mmol), and the reaction afforded compound **6** in 0.57 g yield (83%) with a melting point of 74–76 °C and R_f = 0.54 (A). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 7.99 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.77 (d, J = 7.7 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.60–7.70 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.32–7.50 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.16 (dd, J = 2.5, 7.8 Hz, 1H, ArH), 3.91 (s, 3H, OCH₃); m/z = 276 ([M + H]⁺).

6-Chloro-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-1,3-benzothiazole (7)

The reaction was conducted in a manner similar to the previous procedure. A solution of 6-chloro-*o*-aminothiophenol (0.40 g, 2.5 mmol) in an ethanol–water mixture (1:1, 25 mL) was treated with *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.351 g, 2.5 mmol), and the reaction afforded compound **7** in 0.607 g yield (86.7%) with a melting point of 144–146 °C and R_f = 0.65 (A). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 8.17 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.13 (d, J = 2.2 Hz, 1H, ArH),

7.56 (dt, J = 7.9, 2.2 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.41 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.32 (d, J = 8.1 Hz, 2H, ArH); m/z = 280 ([M + H]⁺). Molecular formula: C₁₃H₇Cl₂NS.

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